

The Role of Atomic Oxygen in the Decomposition of Self-Assembled Monolayers During Area-Selective Atomic Layer Deposition

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Abstract

Utilising self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) to achieve area-selective atomic layer deposition (AS-ALD) as an approach to bottom-up nanofabrication has recently gained significant attention from the nanoelectronics industry. With the continued downscaling of feature sizes, top-down processing can no longer reach the challenging demands of the industry which requires conformal coating of high aspect ratio vias and a reduction in misalignment errors in multi-layered devices. In this work we attempt to imitate the effects of the ALD oxidation pulse experienced by the SAMs during the AS-ALD process by exposing two SAMs of different chain lengths and different functional groups, (3-trimethoxysilylpropyl)diethylenetriamine (DETA) and octadecyltrimethoxysilane (OTMS), to numerous controlled *in-vacuo* atomic oxygen exposures with subsequent characterisation by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). We monitor the sequential removal of the deposited monolayers with each successive atomic oxygen exposure for both SAMs. The etch rate is observed to be distinct for the different SAMs, the amino-terminated short chain DETA SAM reveals a linear etch rate while the longer chain OTMS SAM reveals an exponential etch rate. The results presented provide some insights into what characteristics are important for choosing the correct SAM for AS-ALD applications.

1. Introduction

Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) has greatly enhanced the capability to deposit very uniform and conformal thin films on high aspect ratio structures allowing for the continued downscaling of feature sizes in nanoelectronic devices. ALD is largely compatible with semiconductor device fabrication processes and has many other advantages that make it an attractive deposition method [1–3]. One main drawback for ALD is that the same conformality that leads to uniform deposition across large substrates, leads to increased process complexity when patterning of the surface is required. Area selective ALD (AS-ALD) is proposed as a method

35 for preferentially depositing a material on a specific area on the surface while the remainder is
 36 left uncoated, giving control over a deposited thin film in the horizontal plane[4–8]. One
 37 approach being adopted to achieve area selective ALD is through the use of self-assembled
 38 monolayers (SAMs) which can assist in the patterning of microscale and nanoscale features [9–
 39 16] . The adaptability of the SAM chemistry makes them a prime candidate for selectively
 40 adhering to particular sections of the surface allowing them to block any subsequently deposited
 41 material. Herregods *et al.* describe a bottom-up manufacturing process for electronic devices
 42 in the back-end-of-line (BEOL) which consists of using SAMs to passivate the surface and
 43 consequently block film growth by ALD [17]. Device geometries in the BEOL typically consist
 44 of alternating patterns of metal and dielectric material on the wafer surface and the process
 45 methodology often calls for deposition only on either the metal or the dielectric. In the case of
 46 deposition on the metallic surface, a silane-based SAM can be deposited on the dielectric
 47 surface and by choosing an appropriate terminal functional group it will block the subsequent
 48 deposited material from bonding to the dielectric. In this way the material is only deposited on
 49 the metal and not the dielectric [18–20]. Conversely, using thiol [21] or phosphonic acid-based
 50 [22] SAMs results in material being deposited on the dielectric and not the metal/metal oxide.
 51 The SAM is then removed by etching [23,24] or electrochemically by applying a potential bias
 52 [25]. The area selective process is schematically displayed in Figure 1 (a).

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54

55 *Figure 1 (a) schematic showing the area selective ALD process using a SAM as a blocker, (b) the*
 56 *DETA and OTMS SAM molecules and identification of the different chemical states of carbon within*
 57 *the molecules. Molecule diagrams generated by QuteMol [26].*

58

59 This method can also be used for depositing on 3D nanostructures. Chopra *et al.* have shown
 60 how AS-ALD can differ on planar surfaces and non-planar surfaces. They were able to
 61 selectively block TiN deposition on hafnium dioxide (HfO₂) on the planar surfaces but grow
 62 TiN films on the nano-lines and nano-pillars where the SAM film had difficulty creating a
 63 uniform layer [27]. Dong *et al.* have also demonstrated their AS-ALD technique for
 64 successfully coating the vertical surfaces of nanopillars with zinc oxide (ZnO) [28]. Mameli *et*

65 *al.* have introduced a cyclic style AS-ALD process where inhibitor molecules are reapplied
66 after each cycle [29]. The deposition of dielectrics by ALD, both on metals and dielectric
67 substrates, typically requires oxygen as a co-reactant derived either from water, for example in
68 the trimethylaluminum-based Al_2O_3 process [30], or an oxygen plasma during plasma-
69 enhanced ALD (PE-ALD)[31]. Although the use of plasma allows for a greater range of
70 materials to be deposited, at lower temperatures the films are not as conformal or uniform, and
71 they are known to cause damage to the underlying layers [31–33]. Lee *et al.* have shown how
72 the choice of plasma during AS-ALD can degrade a SAM film up to the point where no
73 selective deposition is observed. By changing their gaseous plasma from an NH_3 to a H_2 they
74 successfully deposited thin cobalt films up to 1000 cycles [34]. An O_2 plasma is frequently used
75 as the reactant plasma for the growth of a range of materials including, Al_2O_3 , HfO_2 , SiO_2 , Pt,
76 Ru, TiO_2 and ZnO [31,32,35] and more recently, molecular oxygen has been utilized for metal
77 oxide deposition [36]. However, O_2 plasmas have been shown to cause degradation of low-*k*
78 dielectric films due to ions and oxygen radicals causing damage to the dielectric [37]. This
79 greatly affects the device performance and circuit reliability. With regards to SAMs, George *et al.*
80 *al.* have shown how an O_2 plasma can be used to etch a 1-octadecanethiol (ODT) SAM and
81 remove it completely from the surface. In their study the SAM, which was deposited on a gold
82 covered Si substrate, was partially covered by a poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) stamp.
83 Subsequently, an O_2 plasma was used to etch the SAM from regions that were not covered by
84 the PDMS stamp, creating a pattern. SEM and AFM performed after the electrodeposition of
85 ZnO, Ni and Ag onto the patterned samples, found that these materials were only deposited on
86 the underlying gold, while the SAM effectively blocked the deposition of these materials [38].
87 Atomic oxygen has been used as an ion-free alternative to O_2 plasma as it has the capacity to
88 be less aggressive because it is a low-energy treatment that is also electrically neutral.
89 Chaudhari *et al.* have assessed the role atomic oxygen plays in O_2 plasma induced damage of
90 ultralow-*k* dielectrics [39]. Bogan *et al.* have used atomic oxygen as a less aggressive
91 replacement for plasma treatment to modify dense low-*k* dielectric surfaces [40]. Dai *et al.*
92 using self-assembled monolayers as a substitute for wool fibres, investigated the impact of
93 atomic oxygen and O_2 plasma on an alkylthiolate SAM. They found that the plasma treatment
94 had a more significant effect and etched the SAM much more rapidly compared to atomic
95 oxygen treatment [41].

96 In an attempt to understand the contribution of atomic oxygen to the decomposition of self-
97 assembled monolayers, the current study examines the impact of controlled atomic oxygen
98 exposures of two SAMs which are of interest for AS-ALD applications. This atomic oxygen
99 treatment essentially mimics the oxidation pulse performed during the ALD cycle without the
100 presence of other species. The stepwise treatment of a (3-trimethoxysilylpropyl)
101 diethylenetriamine (DETA) SAM (Figure 1(b)) is highly controlled using successive 100

102 Langmuir (L) exposures and examined using XPS measurements. The impact of these small
103 atomic oxygen exposures is compared with much larger 1000 L exposures, and the changes
104 induced on the DETA SAM terminated SiO₂ substrate is examined. The same process is
105 followed for the carbon-terminated octadecyltrimethoxysilane (OTMS) SAM (Figure 1(b)),
106 although larger 500 L exposures are used. The etch rate resulting from these oxidation steps for
107 each SAM is studied.

108

109 2. Experimental Details

110 In this work two different SAMs were deposited on Si wafers with a native silicon dioxide layer
111 and subsequently characterised by XPS. The samples were then treated with controlled atomic
112 oxygen exposures, with XPS spectra recorded after each exposure. The Si substrates were
113 initially cleaned by UV-ozone treatment for 15 mins in a Jelight UVO cleaner to generate OH
114 groups at the surface. The SAM films were derived from DETA and OTMS. The DETA was
115 vapour deposited onto the UV-ozone treated substrates at a temperature of 140 °C for one hour
116 at a base pressure of ~10 mbar in a dedicated oven for silane SAM deposition. These are the
117 ideal conditions for DETA deposition taken from earlier work [42]. The OTMS was deposited
118 onto the UV-ozone treated substrates at the slightly higher temperature of 170 °C for one hour
119 at a base pressure of ~10 mbar. 100 µL of each SAM was placed on a glass slide in the oven
120 and allowed to evaporate coating the Si substrates. OTMS was also deposited in the liquid
121 phase. Here an UVO treated Si substrate was submerged in a 10mM solution of OTMS and
122 Toluene for 48 hours and rinsed thoroughly with Toluene afterwards.

123 The SAM samples were then cleaved into 1 cm² coupons and separately loaded into an ultra-
124 high-vacuum (UHV) XPS system for *in-situ* atomic oxygen treatment and analysis. The base
125 pressure of the XPS system was typically ~1 x 10⁻⁹ mbar. XPS was performed using a
126 conventional Mg K α ($h\nu = 1253.6$ eV) X-ray source in conjunction with an electron energy
127 analyser operating at a pass energy of 20 eV giving an overall resolution of 1.2 eV. Samples
128 were not degassed prior to atomic oxygen exposures, so as not to degrade the SAM film. Atomic
129 oxygen exposures were performed at room temperature using an Oxford Applied Research
130 TC50 thermal gas cracker operating at 60 W which was positioned in the line of sight of the
131 sample at a distance of approximately 6 cm. Atomic oxygen is generated by passing molecular
132 oxygen through a heated capillary inside of the gas cracker where it thermally dissociates into
133 atomic oxygen. Molecular oxygen was leaked into the UHV chamber via a needle valve up to
134 an O₂ partial pressure of ~2 x 10⁻⁶ mbar. When the cracker was switched on, the partial pressure
135 of O₂ in the vacuum chamber (monitored by a Dycor LC-100 quadrupole mass spectrometer)
136 is seen to decrease. This decrease is a measure of the efficiency of the cracker at generating
137 atomic oxygen in the system. Using this approach, the exact time for 100 L was calculated for

138 each exposure and any small changes in pressure were accounted for. The atomic oxygen
139 exposures were cumulative with XPS spectra acquired after each exposure. One sample of the
140 DETA SAM received twenty-four successive 100 L exposures followed by three 1000 L
141 exposures and one final 2000 L exposure. A second sample received two successive 1000 L
142 exposures and one 2000 L exposure. The OTMS SAM received nine successive 500 L atomic
143 oxygen exposures, with XPS data recorded after each exposure.

144 All curve fitting analysis presented in this study was performed using AAnalyzer curve fitting
145 software. All spectral peaks are fitted with a Voigt profile which combines both Gaussian and
146 Lorentzian line shapes, and a Shirley-Sherwood type background is used for all core level
147 spectra. The Si 2p spectra are fitted using a Voigt doublet with a peak separation of 0.6 eV and
148 a Lorentzian value of 0.39 eV. The O 1s, N 1s and C 1s are fitted with a single Voigt peak with
149 Lorentzian values of 0.55, 0.5 and 0.3 eV, respectively. The Gaussian element of all component
150 peaks for a particular peak envelope remained constant throughout.

151 Static water contact angle (WCA) measurements were performed to assess if a SAM film had
152 been deposited. A sharp increase in hydrophobicity is observed when a SAM layer is present
153 on the Si surface. The measurements were performed on a DataPhysics OCA 20 Contact Angle
154 System equipped with a Teli CCD camera using the sessile drop method. A droplet of deionized
155 water with a volume $\sim 3 \mu\text{L}$ was dispensed, measured, and then removed by N_2 flow. The water
156 contact angle values quoted in this text are an average of five measurements taken at different
157 points across the sample. The contact angle values were obtained from image analysis using
158 SCA20 software.

159 The thickness of the OTMS SAM layer was obtained from spectroscopic ellipsometry
160 measurements on a J. A. Woollam RC2 Spectroscopic Ellipsometer. Data was acquired at three
161 incident angles 65° , 70° , and 75° with a 5 s acquisition time at each angle, within 200 and 2500
162 nm wavelength, with a beam diameter of 3-4 mm and a beam divergence less than 0.4° . The
163 UVO treated substrate was measured first using a standard Si substrate with native Si oxide
164 model to obtain the thickness of the native SiO_2 and then remeasured following SAM
165 deposition. The thickness of the OTMS was then determined using a Cauchy layer with a
166 refractive index set between 1.35 and 1.50 [43].

167

168 3. Results & Discussions

169 *3.1 Etching of DETA SAM Resulting from Atomic Oxygen Exposures*

170 Figure 2 displays the overall atomic concentration for the DETA SAM on the silicon substrate
171 as measured by XPS throughout the experiment. Unlike conventional quantification methods
172 which assume a homogenous surface, we assume a layered one where the Si/ SiO_2 substrate is
173 attenuated by the SAM layer. It can be seen that as the carbon and nitrogen signals decrease the

174 silicon and oxygen signals increase. This is interpreted as evidence of the removal of the SAM
 175 which exposes more of the underlying oxidised silicon substrate surface and in turn increases
 176 its signal. After the twenty-fourth exposure the carbon and nitrogen signals are just above half
 177 of their original intensity. The larger 1000 L and 2000 L exposures at the end decrease the
 178 intensity of these peaks more rapidly. The SAM is never fully removed from the surface even
 179 though cumulatively the samples have been exposed to 7400 L of atomic oxygen. In order to
 180 understand the changes induced in the SAM following the atomic oxygen exposures, the C 1s
 181 and N 1s core level spectra were studied in detail. An understanding of the component peaks
 182 of the spectra for each element requires analysis of the chemical states of that component within
 183 the DETA molecule.
 184

185
 186 *Figure 2: Overall atomic concentration of the DETA SAM on the oxidised silicon surface from selected*
 187 *atomic oxygen experimental steps. The carbon and nitrogen signals sequentially decrease with each*
 188 *successive exposure.*

189
 190 Figure 1 (b) shows a schematic illustration of both the DETA molecule and the OTMS
 191 molecule, with the individual elements identified. In the case of carbon for the DETA SAM,
 192 we can identify it as existing in three distinct chemical states. The most common of these is
 193 CH₂-CH₂ occurring eight times in the molecule. The next most common state is CH₂-NH,
 194 occurring five times in the molecule. The last chemical state occurs just once and is CH₂-Si. As
 195 such, in an ideal environment it would be expected that three carbon peaks be present in the C
 196 1s spectra, with the CH₂-CH₂ peak the strongest peak. The expected position of these peaks can
 197 be predicted from the electronegativity of the elements involved. In the case of CH₂-NH and
 198 CH₂-CH₂ we expect the C-N related peak to occur at slightly higher binding energy with the
 199 CH₂-Si at slightly lower binding energy to these peaks.

200 Figure 3 (a) and (b) shows the curve fitted C 1s spectra both for the as-deposited DETA SAM
 201 and throughout the course of atomic exposures detailed above, while the decrease of the C1s

202 intensity with atomic oxygen exposure is displayed Figure 3 (c). Prior to atomic oxygen
 203 exposure, the primary component peak is the CH₂-CH₂ peak at 284.8eV [44–47]. Note that
 204 adventitious carbon has a similar binding energy, and the associated peak cannot be resolved.
 205 There is also a peak which we attribute to CH₂-NH at 286.6 eV, which may also include carbon
 206 bonded to oxygen which would be difficult to resolve from C-N bonds. However, there is no
 207 evidence of a peak associated with CH₂-Si at lower binding energy, possibly due to the limited
 208 resolution of the conventional XPS technique.

209

210 *Figure 3 (a) and (b) C 1s spectra showing the overall decrease in component peaks except for the O-*
 211 *C=O peak which grows with higher exposure to atomic oxygen, (c) decomposition of the carbon signal*
 212 *with increasing atomic oxygen exposures up to 2400 L.*

213

214 Notably there are peaks at higher binding energy than the idealized model would account for,
 215 indicating the presence of oxygen. The peak at 286.6 eV may be partially attributed to C-O
 216 bonds as mentioned, and is visible even before any atomic oxygen exposure is carried out
 217 [48,49]. These C-O bonds are also indicative of surface contamination due to atmospheric
 218 exposure, while the C-N bonds are within the SAM. A third component peak visible in the
 219 spectrum at ~ 288.0 eV can be attributed to C=O bonds [48,50]. It appears that some oxygen
 220 has become incorporated into the DETA SAM and has bonded to the nitrogen and/or carbon in
 221 the terminal group. Following the twenty-four 100 L exposure the overall C 1s intensity is
 222 almost half of its original value. However, the growth of an additional peak at ~289.5 eV is
 223 observed and is indicative of O-C=O bonds [48,51]. This peak provides further confirmation
 224 that some oxygen is being incorporated into the DETA film during the atomic oxygen
 225 treatments. The next 1000 L exposure sees a decrease in all peaks except for the O-C=O
 226 component peak. This trend is observed for the subsequent exposures. The final 2000 L
 227 exposure almost completely removes the SAM related signal from the surface. Similarly, the
 228 contour plot of Figure 3(c) demonstrates the decrease in intensity of the C 1s peak following
 229 the twenty-four 100 L exposures. Initially, the CH₂-CH₂ peak, visible as the red area, is very
 230 prominent at the start of the atomic oxygen exposure. As the sample is subjected to more atomic

231 oxygen its intensity decreases until it has roughly the same intensity as the other peaks. The
 232 binding energy positions for all DETA SAM peaks are summarised in Table 1. Also visible in
 233 the spectra is a peak on the lower binding energy side of the main C 1s peak. This is the X-ray
 234 satellite peak as our X-ray source is non monochromated, meaning it can produce minor X-ray
 235 components which have a slightly different energy to our main characteristic X-ray. These
 236 satellite peaks are seen on the lower binding energy side of all the presented spectra. The
 237 decrease in intensity of the CH₂-CH₂ and CH₂-NH component peaks, the increase in intensity
 238 of the C=O peak as well as the growth of the O-C=O peak indicates that two processes are
 239 occurring. Oxygen is being incorporated into the DETA SAM film which results in SAM
 240 decomposition and ultimately the removal of the SAM from the surface.

241

Table 1 Binding energy positions for DETA SAM.

C 1s	BE (eV)	N 1s	BE (eV)	O 1s	BE (eV)
CH ₂ -CH ₂	284.8	CH ₂ -NH	399.3	SiO ₂	532
CH ₂ -NH	286.6	N-O	400.5	O-C	530.3
C=O	288				
O-C=O	289.5				

242

243 The corresponding curve fitted N 1s spectra are shown in Figure 4 (a) and (b) and the decline
 244 of the N 1s intensity in Figure 4 (c). The initial N 1s contains two component peaks that have
 245 been attributed to CH₂-NH bonds at 399.3 eV [52] and a small component peak at 400.5 eV
 246 consistent with N-O bonds [50]. Again, this N-O component is due to oxygen bonding to
 247 nitrogen atoms in the terminal group and the chain. Similar to the C 1s, after the twenty-fourth
 248 100 L exposure there is a large decrease in the overall intensity of the N 1s leaving it at just
 249 above half of its original intensity. With the larger subsequent exposures, the overall intensity
 250 decreases. However, the N-O peak appears not to decrease at the same rate compared to the
 251 CH₂-NH peak.

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Figure 4 (a) and (b) Peak fitted N 1s spectra for selected experimental steps of the atomic oxygen exposures of the DETA SAM, (c) shows with each 100 L exposure the N 1s peak intensity decreases.

256

257 The loss of peak intensity for both the C 1s and N 1s alludes to two possible mechanisms for
258 the etching of the DETA SAM. The atomic oxygen can be desorbing small moieties at a time
259 or the intact DETA chains are being desorbed [53]. The carbon-nitrogen ratio plotted in Figure
260 5(a) as a function of oxygen exposure remains virtually constant over the course of the
261 experiment. The overall reduction in intensity for the C 1s and N 1s signals as a function of
262 treatment, shown in Figure 5(b), points to an etching process where the full chain is removed
263 from the surface.

264

265 *Figure 5 (a) The carbon nitrogen ratio is maintained throughout the experiment. (b) The C 1s and N 1s*
266 *plotted as a function of atomic oxygen treatment showing the magnitude of the total reduction in these*
267 *signals with atomic oxygen exposures.*

268

269 The O 1s and the Si 2p spectra illustrated in Figure 6 (a) and (b), respectively, show very little
270 change in peak profile over the course of the experiment. Two component peaks are visible in
271 the O 1s which are associated with SiO₂ at 532 eV and C-O at 530.3 eV [54]. The intensity of the
272 SiO₂ component peak is much larger than the C-O peak making it difficult to observe
273 changes in the carbon-oxygen bonding environment. A small change in the Si 2p can be
274 associated with the formation of sub-oxides after exposure. Cole et al. determined a method for
275 accurate thickness measurement of a SiO₂ overlayer on silicon, based on the ratio of the silicon
276 bulk signal to the silicon oxide signal [55]. Previously it has been shown that using this method,

277 one can see an increase in thickness of the SiO₂ on silicon when a silane SAM has been
 278 deposited [44]. This signifies that the anchor group of the SAM has bonded to the SiO₂ layer.
 279 Using this method thickness calculations on the SiO₂ peak reveal that there is no change in the
 280 thickness of the SiO₂ after any of the exposures. This would suggest that the Si-O anchoring
 281 group of the DETA is unaffected by the atomic oxygen treatments, whereas the rest of the SAM
 282 is progressively removed.

283

284 *Figure 6 O 1s (a) and Si 2p (b) spectra show little to no change over the course of the study.*

285

286 3.2 Etching of OTMS due to Atomic Oxygen Exposure

287 OTMS is a long chain SAM, with 18 carbon atoms in the hydrocarbon chain as schematically
 288 shown in Figure 1 (b). It is approximately 2.4 nm in length which makes it just over twice as
 289 long as the DETA molecule. The OTMS also has no nitrogen containing terminal functional
 290 group, it contains just the silane anchoring group and the hydrocarbon chain. For the OTMS
 291 SAM we can identify the carbon as existing in two distinct chemical states CH₂-CH₂ and CH₂-
 292 Si. During this study, the OTMS received nine 500 L in situ atomic oxygen exposures. It was
 293 presumed that due to the chain length that the smaller 100 L exposures would take a
 294 considerable amount of time to etch the SAM. On the other hand, the 1000 L exposures were
 295 considered too large to observe the stepwise etching of the SAM. Figure 7 displays the chemical
 296 composition for the OTMS throughout the course of the study. A steady decrease of the C 1s
 297 is observed with each atomic oxygen exposure. This corresponds to the removal of the OTMS
 298 SAM from the surface. As the C 1s signal intensity decreases the O 1s and Si 2p signals
 299 increase. Just as with the DETA SAM, as the OTMS is etched from the surface, more of the
 300 underlying SiO₂ substrate is uncovered and this in turn increases the intensity of the Si and O
 301 signals.

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Figure 7 : Overall atomic concentration of the OTMS SAM on the oxidised silicon surface after each atomic oxygen exposure. The carbon signal sequentially decreases with each successive exposure.

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It is worth noting from the atomic concentration that the OTMS has a lower percentage of carbon than the DETA even though the OTMS molecule contains more carbon. To investigate this further two more OTMS samples were fabricated, one by the vapour method and the other by the liquid method. The atomic concentrations of these samples can be seen in supplemental information (SI) Fig. S1, where it is observed that there is a discrepancy in the carbon content between the vapour deposited sample which contains 19.7% carbon and the liquid deposited sample which contains 35.1% carbon. However, water contact angle measurements (Fig. S2) performed before and after OTMS vapour deposition show the nature of the surface has been transformed from being hydrophilic to hydrophobic. This change in surface energy is indicative of deposition of a SAM layer on the surface. Comparing this to the liquid deposited sample we can see the WCA values are very similar, and both are greater than 100°. Ellipsometry measurements (Fig. S2) conclude that a SAM film has indeed been deposited by the vapour method, but it only has a thickness of 1.2 ± 0.1 nm considerably less than would be expected from an OTMS film. The liquid deposited film is close to the actual length of the OTMS SAM with a thickness of 2.6 ± 0.2 nm. Thence our vapour deposition method was varied to test the efficacy of the process. Several more samples were fabricated from the vapour method where the deposition time and temperature were varied, and these results are discussed in SI and can be seen in Fig S3. From these results it can be seen that deposition at 170 °C for 60 mins appears to be the optimal deposition conditions for the OTMS SAM. Thickness variation across the surface can be seen in Fig. S4. It is well known that liquid deposited SAMs create a near ideal monolayer film which are well ordered and densely packed, with the SAM molecules “standing up”. Iwasa *et al.* investigated the in-situ deposition of an OTMS SAM from the liquid phase using high-speed AFM [56]. They observed that during the nucleation stage OTMS molecules can form domains, nanometres in diameter. Additionally, they were able to show that the SAM-

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331 substrate interactions were not as important as the lateral polymerization between adjoining
332 SAM molecules in forming a highly ordered dense film. However, during vapour deposition
333 the OTMS molecule does not appear to form the same type of dense film. It is postulated that
334 the SAM film when deposited in the vapour phase forms a much more disordered and less dense
335 film where the OTMS molecules are predominantly in a lying down phase or in a partial
336 standing up phase leading to less SAM-SAM interactions [57]. To the best of the authors
337 knowledge no in-situ experiments detailing the mechanisms of deposition of a SAM from the
338 vapour phase are available. It is clear that there exists a difference between the SAM layer
339 deposited by liquid and vapour deposition methods. Although it is outside the scope of this
340 article, it is an important area to investigate as depositing a high-quality SAM layer using a
341 vapour method can significantly decrease deposition time and make the process more
342 environmentally friendly thereby providing an attractive avenue for implementation into
343 industry.

344

345 The corresponding O 1s spectra for the vapour deposited OTMS in Figure 8 (a) are dominated
346 by the SiO₂ component peak at a binding energy of 532.2 eV. On the lower binding energy side
347 at 530.5 eV, is the presence of a small peak related to C-O bonds, which is also observed in the
348 C 1s spectra [54]. There is little change in these two peaks over the course of the experiment.
349 The SiO₂ component signal intensity does increase slightly due to the removal of the SAM.

350

351

352 *Figure 8 The O 1s (a) shows little change due to atomic oxygen exposure while the C 1s (b) shows the*
353 *incorporation of oxygen into the SAM layer and (c) shows a dramatic decrease in C 1s intensity.*

354

355 The C 1s spectrum shown in Figure 8 (b), displays a peak profile in the as loaded spectrum
356 which can be curve fitted using two component peaks. The main component peak is the CH₂-
357 CH₂ peak at a binding energy of 284.8 eV. On the higher binding energy side is the presence
358 of a C-O peak at 286.1 eV [51]. Following the first 500 L atomic oxygen exposure the
359 emergence of an additional peak on the higher binding energy side is observed at 288.1 eV.

360 This peak is indicative of C=O bonds beginning to form which suggests that the oxygen is being
 361 incorporated into the film. A decrease in the intensity of the main component peak is also
 362 observed. With the subsequent atomic oxygen exposures, the CH₂-CH₂ peak decreases further
 363 and by the fifth 500 L exposure its intensity has been diminished to less than half of its original
 364 value. The C-O peak has not changed considerably while the C=O peak has increased slightly.
 365 By the final 500 L exposure the carbon has almost been fully removed by the atomic oxygen.
 366 This is clearly seen in the contour plot in Figure 8(c). As with the DETA SAM, there is no CH₂-
 367 Si peak observed in the C 1s spectra of the OTMS SAM. Binding energy positions for the
 368 OTMS peaks are shown in Table 2. Repeating the method from Cole *et al.* SiO₂ thickness
 369 calculations performed from the Si 2p peak (data not shown) show no change in thickness of
 370 the SiO₂ due to atomic oxygen exposure signifying that the Si-O anchoring group remains
 371 unaffected, chemically bonded to the surface.

372

Table 2 Binding energy positions for OTMS SAM.

C 1s	BE (eV)	O 1s	BE (eV)
CH ₂ -CH ₂	284.8	SiO ₂	532.2
C-O	286.1	O-C	530.5
C=O	288.1		

373

374

375 3.3 Decay Rate of the DETA and the OTMS SAMs

376 To examine the rate at which the DETA was etched from the surface due to the atomic oxygen,
 377 the intensities of the C 1s and N 1s after each exposure were plotted. Both the small (100 L)
 378 and large (1000 L) exposures are plotted to reveal essentially linear rates of etching for both
 379 the C 1s and N 1s, as seen in Figure 9 (a) and (b), respectively. It would not be unreasonable to
 380 expect that the as-received DETA SAM treated sample would have some DETA molecules
 381 present which are not chemically bonded on the surface. These unreacted molecules should be
 382 easily desorbed, and this is reflected in the significant decrease in both the C 1s and N 1s
 383 intensities from the as loaded to the first atomic oxygen exposure. The initial intensity for the
 384 larger exposures is less than for the short 100 L exposures as these unreacted molecules have
 385 already desorbed. From these graphs it is clear that the etch rate is determined by the sum total
 386 of the atomic oxygen exposures, as ten individual 100 L exposures produces the same results
 387 as a single 1000 L exposure.

388

389 *Figure 9 Etching of the DETA SAM in (a) shows the decrease in intensity of the C 1s and (b) displays*
 390 *the decrease in intensity of the N 1s. Both graphs show a linear decay of the DETA SAM. The etching*
 391 *of the OTMS SAM is shown in (c) where the decrease of the C 1s follows an exponential trend.*

392

393 The decrease in intensity of the C 1s signal for the OTMS SAM is shown in Figure 9 (c) and is
 394 fitted with an exponential function in contrast to the DETA SAM which shows a linear trend.

395 Torres *et al.* using a gas cracker, investigated the interaction between a C₁₆ thiol SAM deposited
 396 on gold with atomic oxygen [51]. They suggested that there were three stages in the etching of
 397 the SAM. In the first stage (0 – 60 mins.) the oxygen atoms attached themselves to the
 398 hydrocarbon chain. In stage two (60 – 360 mins.) the etching of the SAMs is initiated with the
 399 removal of small moieties from the hydrocarbon chain. Essentially, there is a balance between
 400 oxidising the SAM and etching the SAM. The final stage (> 360 mins.) sees a change in how
 401 the SAM is removed. In this stage the oxygen is able to permeate to the gold interface and can
 402 oxidise the surface as well as etching the remaining SAM. Their study showed that the etching
 403 starts off linearly but changes to a more exponential rate the more the SAM becomes oxidised.
 404 This three-stage process is not observed here for either the DETA or OTMS SAM. The
 405 exposures used in this present study are much smaller and show greater control over the
 406 removal of the SAM.

407 Gorham *et al.* used atomic hydrogen to investigate the etching of thiol SAMs of various chain
 408 lengths (C₉, C₁₂, C₁₆ and C₁₈) deposited on gold [58]. They found that shorter chains are
 409 desorbed rapidly from the surface in both small segments and full chains. The longer chains,
 410 however, resist the atomic hydrogen permeating to the gold surface and so are removed in

411 smaller moieties. Their study shows that a C₁₈ SAM displayed an exponential etch rate which
412 is in good agreement with this current study as can be seen in Figure 9 (c).

413 It is thought that the terminal group in the DETA SAM gives some protection to oxidation of
414 the hydrocarbon chain, while the OTMS SAM has no terminal group to offer this protection, it
415 is purely a hydrocarbon chain. Hence it could be more difficult for the atomic oxygen to
416 permeate the DETA layer as a well ordered densely packed film needs to be breached, before
417 the oxygen-carbon interactions which lead to the etching process can commence. Once the
418 oxygen can reach the SiO₂ interface it can then remove the hydrocarbon chain and terminal
419 amine group of the DETA in one step. The OTMS on the other hand, cannot stop the atomic
420 oxygen penetrating the SAM layer to initiate the etching process as it does not have a terminal
421 group to provide this protection. This leaves the oxygen free to directly bond to the hydrocarbon
422 chain and remove smaller moieties by oxidation. This leads to a much quicker initial etching of
423 the film as seen by the exponential dependence. From the atomic concentration of the DETA
424 SAM in Figure 2 it can be seen that following 4400 L of atomic oxygen, that ~10.7% of the
425 surface signal is from the carbon. However, as seen in Figure 7 following 4500 L of atomic
426 oxygen only ~3% of the surface signal of the OTMS is from the presence of carbon. Even
427 though the OTMS chain length is longer than the DETA, this offers little extra protection
428 against etching. It appears as if the terminal group plays a critical role in determining the atomic
429 etch rate as it can offer more protection to resist etching than a longer hydrocarbon chain.

430

431 Conclusion

432 Overall, due to excellent control of atomic oxygen exposures the stepwise etching of a SAM is
433 observed. Upon loading both the DETA and OTMS SAMs, the photoemission spectra are
434 essentially as expected, given their chemical composition. In the DETA SAM there is evidence
435 of existing oxygen bonds in the photoemission spectra of as-received sample which has been
436 attributed to atmospheric exposure. As part of the etching process for the DETA, the atomic
437 oxygen appears to strip the terminal groups and hydrocarbon chain from the SiO₂. The integrity
438 of the residual DETA SAM remains intact as seen by the constant carbon nitrogen ratio
439 throughout the etch process. The DETA SAM is observed to be etched from the surface in a
440 linear manner which is independent of the exposure magnitude. For the OTMS SAM, the
441 emergence of C=O bonds in the C 1s suggest that the atomic oxygen is incorporating itself into
442 the hydrocarbon chain before desorbing small segments of the chain. These treatments of both
443 the DETA and the OTMS terminated SiO₂ substrates result in no observable change in the Si
444 2p spectra thus implying that the anchoring group remains unaffected by the atomic oxygen
445 treatments. The decay of the OTMS SAM photoemission signal appears to be exponential in
446 nature, with the removal of small moieties. It appears that the terminal group in the DETA,

447 inhibits fast diffusion of oxygen into the monolayer. This stops oxygen bonding to the DETA
448 chain which in turn slows down the removal of the DETA from the surface. The long chain of
449 the OTMS appears to offer less protection to etching of the SAM layer. The oxygen can readily
450 diffuse into the SAM and bond to the hydrocarbon chain, removing small moieties even after
451 the first exposure. This could be very useful when deciding on what SAM to use for AS-ALD
452 applications as a more robust SAM is required.

453

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461

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